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Addiction Laboratory

A SCOPING REVIEW PROTOCOL

The Role of Induced-Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) Model in Untangling the Etiology of Substance Use Disorders

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The Role of Induced-Pluripotent Stem Cell (iPSC) Model in Untangling the Etiology of Substance Use Disorders: A Scoping Review Protocol

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

GLOSSARY	- 4 -
INTRODUCTION & STUDY RATIONALE	- 6 -
Study Rationale	- 6 -
METHODS	- 7 -
Study Design	- 7 -
Study Protocol	- 7 -
Study Framework	- 8 -
Stage I. Review objectives/questions	- 8 -
Inclusion and exclusion criteria.....	- 8 -
Stage II. Evidence sources and search strategy	- 10 -
Sources and type of evidence	- 10 -
Search strategy and terms	- 10 -
Stage III. Study selection	- 11 -
Pilot testing.....	- 11 -
Screening and selection	- 12 -
Stage IV. Data extraction	- 12 -
Stage V. Data analysis and presentation	- 13 -
Stage VI. Collaborative consultation	- 13 -
ETHICS & DISSEMINATION	- 13 -
LIMITATIONS	- 13 -
CONCLUSIONS	- 14 -
REFERENCES	- 16 -
TABLE	- 21 -
Table 1. A draft of data extraction form.	- 21 -

GLOSSARY

The glossary lists abbreviations and classification of controlled substances used in the protocol.

Appendix 1. Lists of abbreviations.

Abbreviation	Definition and Details
ESC	Embryonic stem cell
hESC	Human embryonic stem cell
iPSC	Induced pluripotent stem cell
IRR	interrater reliability
LSD	Lysergic acid diethylamide, a potent hallucinogen, is a Schedule I substance under the Controlled Substances Act*.
MDA	3,4-Methylenedioxyamphetamine, known as “sally” and “sass”, a drug of the amphetamine family, is a Schedule I substance under the CSA.
MDMA	3,4- Methylenedioxymethamphetamine, also known as “ecstasy”, “molly”, or “mandy”, an illegal drug with mixing stimulant and hallucinogen effects, is a Schedule I substance under the CSA.
MPTP	1-methyl-4-phenyl-1,2,3,6-tetrahydropyridine, also known as “new heroin”, a by-product of 1-Methyl-4-phenyl-4-propionoxypiperidine (MPPP, a Schedule I substance under the CSA) – a synthetic opioid drug.
PCC	P articipants, C oncepts, and C ontexts
PCP	Phencyclidine, an illegal drug hallucinogen, is a Schedule II substance under the CSA.
PICO	P opulation, I ntervention, C omparison groups, O utcomes model
PRISMA-P	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Protocols
PRISMA-ScR	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews
SUD	Substance use disorder
WOS	Web of Science

CSA, The Controlled Substance Act – a federal U.S. drug policy.

Appendix 2. Schedule classification of controlled substances^a.

Controlled substances under the Controlled Substances Act (CSA), a federal U.S. drug policy, are classified into five schedules.

Schedule	Definition and Details
Schedule I	Drugs, substances, or chemicals <i>with no currently accepted medical use and a high potential for abuse.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples: heroin, lysergic acid diethylamide (LSD), marijuana (cannabis), 3,4-methylenedioxymethamphetamine (ecstasy), methaqualone, and peyote.
Schedule II	Drugs, substances, or chemicals <i>with a high potential for abuse, with use potentially leading to severe psychological or physical dependence.</i> These drugs are also considered <i>dangerous.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples: combination products with less than 15 milligrams of hydrocodone per dosage unit (Vicodin), cocaine, methamphetamine, methadone, hydromorphone (Dilaudid), meperidine (Demerol), oxycodone (OxyContin), fentanyl, Dexedrine, Adderall, and Ritalin.
Schedule III	Drugs, substances, or chemicals <i>with a moderate to low potential for physical and psychological dependence.</i> Schedule III drugs abuse potential is less than Schedule I and Schedule II drugs but more than Schedule IV. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples: products containing less than 90 milligrams of codeine per dosage unit (Tylenol with codeine), ketamine, anabolic steroids, testosterone.
Schedule IV	Drugs, substances, or chemicals <i>with a low potential for abuse and low risk of dependence.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples: Xanax, Soma, Darvon, Darvocet, Valium, Ativan, Talwin, Ambien, Tramadol
Schedule V	Drugs, substances, or chemicals <i>with lower potential for abuse than Schedule IV and consist of preparations containing limited quantities of certain narcotics.</i> These drugs are generally used for antidiarrheal, antitussive, and analgesic purposes. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Examples: cough preparations with less than 200 milligrams of codeine or per 100 milliliters (Robitussin AC), Lomotil, Motofen, Lyrica, Parepectolin

^a Data from: United States Drug Enforcement Administration. Drug scheduling [Internet]. Drug information. Springfield, VA: DEA, the U.S. Department of Justice; c2023 [updated 2018 Jul 10; cited 2023 Jan 29]. [2 screens]. Available from: <https://www.dea.gov/drug-information/drug-scheduling>

INTRODUCTION & STUDY RATIONALE

Induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) are a type of stem cell that are generated from adult somatic cells by genetic reprogramming technologies via transcription factors.¹⁻³ iPSCs possess the properties of self-renewal and pluripotency similar to embryonic stem cells (ESCs),¹⁴ enabling them to differentiate into any cell types of germ layers, i.e., ectoderm, mesoderm, and endoderm. The cellular reprogramming was firstly demonstrated by Yamanaka in mice fibroblasts using the four transcription factors of *SOX2*, *KLF4*, *POU5F1*, and *c-MYC* mediated by retrovirus in 2006.⁵ Later, he successfully reprogrammed human fibroblasts into iPSCs using the same method in 2007.⁶ Since then, there have been gradually increasing in application of reprogramming technique in various organisms and cell types, such as retinal pigment epithelium, cardiomyocytes, hepatocytes, and neurons, and become more widespread employed in the research and clinical application.^{12 7-9} Moreover, the use of iPSCs minimizes the bioethical concerns (i.e., destruction or production of human embryos, and genetic manipulation of human embryonic stem cells [hESCs]) that are raised in hESC research.^{10 11} Nonetheless, there are ethical and legal issues for using iPSCs in research and treatments to be addressed (e.g., privacy and confidentiality of personal/genetic information, informed consent, and manufacturing and quality control of the cells).^{12 13}

The generation of iPSCs has opened a new era in biomedical health research via the comparison of the cells derived from “healthy” and “unhealthy” individuals.^{1 4 7-9} The patient-derived iPSCs specific to a certain disease phenotype, serving as ‘disease modeling’, can unveil the biological, molecular, and developmental mechanisms of that disease and provide the future potential treatments.^{9 14-19} When combined with other technological advances, such as gene editing, iPSCs have been shown to facilitate the decomposition of genetic-phenotypic correlation in order to explore the mechanisms of diseases, drug development and discovery.^{16 18 20-24}

Notably, the iPSC model has become a valuable resource for cell-based therapies and organ transplantation.^{9 23 25-27} Advancing therapies using patient-specific iPSCs, in turn, has emerged to the translation medicine; for instance, personalized treatments^{24 27 28} and clinical trials.^{29 30} The pioneering use of iPSCs in clinical treatment was established for retinal degenerative disease in 2014^{31 32} and then Parkinson’s disease in 2018.^{26 33} Later, with the progression in iPSC techniques, patient-derived iPSCs have been used in clinical trials for various diseases such as cancers,³⁴ neuropsychiatric diseases,^{35 36} regenerative diseases,^{25 37} in both therapeutic and non-therapeutic purposes.

Study Rationale

Substance use disorder (SUD) or substance addiction is a common psychiatric disorder, affecting greater than 2% of the world’s population.³⁸ In 2021, 46.3 million Americans aged 12 years and older had been classified as substance users.³⁹ SUDs are also a leading cause of death, accounting for more than 11 million lives lost annually globally (Global Burden Health, 2019).⁴⁰ The iPSC model has been increasingly used in psychiatric disorders,⁴¹⁻⁴⁵ prominently in schizophrenia⁴⁶⁻⁴⁸ and bipolar disorder,⁴⁹⁻⁵¹ but not SUDs during the past decade. A systematic review of iPSC technologies in psychiatric disorders⁵² recently reported a small portion (10%, 6 out of total 56 papers) that focused on SUDs compared to other psychiatric disorders, such as autistic spectrum disorder (6 papers),^{53 54} schizophrenia (23 papers),^{46 47} and bipolar disorder (11 papers).^{49 50} Note that only three commonly used substances (alcohol [4 papers]; nicotine and opioid [one paper for each]) were included in McNeill et al.’s review.

To ensure a comprehensive survey of existing applications of the iPSC model to the substance use field, we scanned the literature using the Cochrane Database of Systematic Review (University of York, York, UK; <https://www.cochrane.org/>), and PROSPERO (National Institute for Health [NIHR], UK). We found that there were no systematic reviews on this topic. As such, we proceeded to research the same topic in PubMed® (National Institutes of Health [NIH], USA), limited to studies published in English and from 1991 to 2021, using quick, gross search terms constructed by combining two strategies: “iPSC” **and** “research areas of interest”. After this retrieval search (on 23 February 2022; updated on 28 December 2022), we discovered an increasing trend of cumulative evidence on iPSC and a variety of research areas, including substance use disorders (see **Supplementary Material 1A**). In brief, the prevalence gradually grew after the first reprogramming of human fibroblasts launched in 2007⁶ and have been steadily rising since 2014,³² when the first human iPSCs clinical trial occurred. However, there were fewer records of “iPSC and substance use disorders” when compared to iPSC and other fields (see details in **Supplementary Material 1B**), suggesting that the iPSC model was used less commonly in SUDs. These findings, similar to a recent report,⁵² demonstrate that the application of the iPSC model to SUDs has been limited. Moreover, when looking into the application of the iPSC model to six commonly used substances (i.e., alcohol, amphetamines, cannabis, cigarette, cocaine, and opioid), we found that alcohol and cigarette use were the most frequently studied categories. Based on these preliminary findings, we presumably conclude that there is a knowledge gap that partly arises from the lack of application of the iPSC model to studying substances of abuse.

Up until now, to our knowledge, no comprehensive review of evidence on the implication of iPSC model specifically to substance use research has been reported. Given the gap, we sought to conduct a scoping review of this topic. A scoping review is a systematic knowledge synthesis tool, which aims to map existing evidence on the topic of interests⁵⁵⁻⁵⁸. We opted to conduct a scoping review in order to achieve our goal of identifying knowledge gaps in the substance use field as they pertain to the application of the iPSC model. Here, we present the scoping review protocol that aims to collate the breadth of evidence, describe background knowledge on the role of iPSC model in SUDs focusing on biomedical or health science research, and ultimately identify gaps in the field.

METHODS

Study Design

This scoping review is being conducted following the methodological framework and guidelines from Arksey and O'Malley⁵⁹⁻⁶⁰ and the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI).⁶¹⁻⁶⁴ We will comply with the reporting guideline – the PRISMA-ScR (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Scoping Reviews) checklist⁶⁵⁻⁶⁶ to report our scoping review.

Study Protocol

The study protocol is based on the methodological framework and guidelines for conduction scoping reviews.⁵⁹⁻⁶⁴ Our protocol reported recommended items (**Supplementary Material 2**) in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for Protocols (PRISMA-P)⁶⁴⁻⁶⁷⁻⁶⁸ for enhancing transparency and reproducibility. The draft had been reviewed and revised by all team members. The final protocol was submitted (on 9 May 2023) and publicly available on Zenodo (Genève, Switzerland; <https://zenodo.org/>) via

doi:10.5281/zenodo.7915253. In addition, whenever we amend this protocol, the rational details including explanation of the update will be acknowledged and posted as an upcoming version on the protocol registry depository.

Study Framework

A methodological framework of conducting scoping reviews was first proposed by Arksey and O'Malley,⁵⁹ and has been periodically updated by Levac, Colquhoun, and O'Brian⁶⁰ and the Joanna Briggs Institute (JBI)⁶¹⁻⁶³ with the most recent version in 2022.⁶⁴ Briefly, our study protocol has adopted six main stages of the framework⁵⁹ as follows: (i) **Stage 1:** identifying the research question (ii) **Stage 2:** identifying relevant studies (iii) **Stage 3:** study selection (iv) **Stage 4:** charting the data (v) **Stage 5:** collating, summarizing, and reporting the result and (vi) **Optional stage:** consultation exercise. We plan to consult with experts in the areas of stem cells and SUDs, albeit an optional stage, stage 6 – consultation, in order to enhance the broad and in-depth range of point of view into our review.

Stage I. Review objectives/questions

Our main objectives are to chart and report an overview of the role of the iPSC model in substance use or addiction research, including additional influencing factors (i.e., iPSC hosts, substances, and main findings), and ultimately to identify the gaps in the application of iPSC model in this field.

Our primary question focused on how the iPSC model has been applied or used in substance use or addiction research?

The review will answer **the specific questions:**

- Question 1** What are detailed characteristics of the iPSC models that have been used?
- Question 2** Which addictive drugs/substances have been studied?
- Question 3** What are the main findings/outcomes that were identified in these studies?
- Question 4** What are the gaps and limitations of the use of iPSC model in substance use or addiction research?

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

We adopted the '**PCC**' – Participant, Concept, and Context components recommended by the JBI Manual Guidance^{61 62} on developing the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Each of the '**PCC**' elements is detailed further.

Inclusion criteria

- **Participants:** Our review defines participants as human and non-human research subjects that were the subjects of the iPSC model used in the studies. Definitely, these subjects – 'iPSC host' are donors whose tissue samples were derived into pluripotent stem cells, which were further examined in the experiment. Non-human subjects (e.g., mice, rats, pigs, and non-human primates) are also considered. No subject restriction on gender, age, or underlying health conditions (i.e., healthy, medical conditions, or pregnancy). Disease conditions can be attributed by direct or indirect effect from the exposure of drug/substance.
- **Concepts:** Three main concepts are required as follows:

- ***Intervention:*** This review aims to investigate an induced pluripotent stem cell approach, specific to a model that induces somatic tissues to pluripotent stem cells using the *reprogramming process*. The iPSC model can be used alone or in combination with other methodological platforms in the studies. Any iPSC-derived cell types are included.
- ***Drug/Substance exposure:*** To address SUDs, studies must involve *addictive drugs or substances*. These drugs/substances are defined as substances that cause the behavior of *drug seeking and misuse* even with significantly adverse health consequence.⁶⁹ In our review, the addictive drugs/substances mainly cause SUDs and are referred to in the following resources: (i) The National Institute on Drug Abuse (NIDA),⁷⁰ the National Institutes of Health (NIH), U.S. Department of Health and Human Services; (ii) The Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration (SAMHSA),³⁹ U.S. Department of Health and Human Services; and (iii) The United States Drug Enforcement Administration (DEA),^{71 72} U.S. Department of Justice.

In addition to well-known narcotic substances: non-controlled (i.e., alcohol, and cigarettes/nicotine/tobacco) and controlled (e.g., amphetamines, cannabis, cocaine, and opioids) (according to the Controlled Substances Act (CSA) in the U.S.), other drugs/substances related to addiction, dependence, or misuse (e.g., kratom, and sport doping substances), including addiction treatment medications are also considered. There is no limitation on types, routes, and time (i.e., short-term and long-term) of exposure. Any sources or forms (e.g., natural, synthetic, and metabolites/derivatives) of substances are not restricted. The testing condition also includes *in vitro* (laboratory testing) and *in vivo* (clinical/medical testing) exposure.

- ***Outcomes:*** This review searches for study outcomes or findings related or relevant to *biomedicine or health science* with an extensive scope of direct and indirect effects from drug/substance exposure. This includes various health issues and is not limited to specific organ or tissue involvement. It will inform answers to this scoping reviews questions.
- **Contexts:**
 - No study geographic location restriction.
 - No limitation on study settings (i.e., academia, industries, government/federal organization, non-government organization, and combined).
 - Studies are in the area of biomedical research or relevant to medical or health science, for example, cellular/biological/molecular research, genetic research, drug discovery, and drug response, etc. Clinical trials are also included.
 - Any types of study designs (i.e., observational, qualitative, and true-/quasi-experimental) are considered, however the application of iPSC model is required in the studies, as either a single model or a combination with other models.

Exclusion criteria

- Studies that did not use reprogramming techniques to generate stem cells such as embryonic stem cells, without a combination with iPSC model.
- Studies that applied other experimental models such as brain slices, post-mortem brain tissues, without a combination with iPSC model.

- Studies that did *not* involve additive drugs/substances or drugs/substances related to substance use behavior (i.e., addiction, dependence, or misuse).
- Studies that were *not* relevant to our review objectives/questions such as food and agricultures, environment, and material sciences.
- Articles that were published *out of the time frame: before 1 January 2007 and after 31 March 2022*.
- Articles that were *not* primary research, systematic review, or meta-analysis studies, i.e., book chapter, other types of review papers, protocols, guidelines, theses and dissertations, editorial or expert comments, abstract conferences, reports, and grey materials.
- Articles that were published in other languages, *not* in English.

Stage II. Evidence sources and search strategy

Sources and type of evidence

Our search aims to capture evidence from primary research, considered to be the best suitable resource to provide information for our review questions. We searched four electronic databases as follows: PubMed® (*The United States National Library of Medicine, the National Institutes of Health*), Embase® (*Elsevier*), Web of Science™ Core Collection (*Science Citation Index Expanded, Social Sciences Citation Index, Arts & Humanities Citation Index, Emerging Sources Citation Index, Conference Proceedings Citation Index, Book Citation Index, and Current Chemical Reactions, Index Chemicus*), and Scopus® (*Elsevier*) with the limited time period from 1 January 2007 to 31 March 2022. The rationale for starting our search in 2007 was because the iPSC model was first established by Yamanaka in 2006.⁴ The search was also restricted to articles published in English, since English is the only language that all team members can read.

Search strategy and terms

Initial search and search development

An initial search, led by the team leader (WN) and facilitated by team members (SRP and RHCP), was comprised of **two concepts** [search terms]: (i) **iPSC**: ["induced pluripotent" OR "iPS" OR "iPSC"] **AND** (ii) **addictive drugs or substances**: ["substance*" OR "addict*" OR "abuse" OR "dependence" OR "use disorder*" OR "substance use" OR "drug use"] OR ["alcohol" OR "cocaine" OR "opioid" OR "smoking*" OR "amphetamine*" OR "methamphetamine*" OR "marijuana" OR "cannabis" OR "nicotine" OR "cigarette"]. Our primary search was executed in the four databases: PubMed, Embase, Web of Science (WOS), and Scopus, in February 2022 (on 28 February 2022), in order to define the feasibility of existing articles relevant to our topic of interest.

The search produced a decent number ($N = 3954$) of records for each database even when limited to the English language: PubMed ($n = 678$), Embase ($n = 933$), WOS ($n = 935$), and Scopus ($n = 1407$). The initial search terms were reviewed and refined to generate a final search strategy in order to assure that our search would identify the articles that were relevant to the objective and questions of our scoping review.

Search strategy

We applied **two concepts** with search terms in the final search strategy as follows:

- **Concept 1 – iPSC:** ("induced pluripotent" OR iPS OR iPSC OR hiPSC OR organoid* OR "pluripotent stem cell*").

AND

- **Concept 2 – Addictive drugs or substances:** (substance* OR alcohol* OR ethanol* OR narcotic* OR cocaine OR opioid* OR amphetamine* OR meth OR methamphetamine* OR marijuana OR cannab* OR nicotin* OR tobacco OR cigar* OR smoke* OR smoking OR psychoactive OR psychostimulant* OR MPTP OR MDA OR MDMA OR addict* OR abus* OR habit* OR misuse* OR user* OR hallucinoge* OR "illicit drug*" OR "illegal drug*" OR depressants).

The search terms and indexed terms were adapted according to the format of each database. Full search strategies for all four databases can be seen at **Supplementary Material 3**. The search aimed to capture published articles of primary research studies or systematic reviews, which are likely to provide key evidence to answer our review questions. The final search was completed across PubMed, Embase, WOS, and Scopus by a team member (SRP), a research informationist.

Our final search identified a total of 5983 primary research records via four electronic databases (PubMed, Embase, WOS, and Scopus), which were imported into EndNote™ version 20 (Clarivate™, London, UK). After removing duplicates ($n = 3106$), 2877 records remained for further study selection.

Stage III. Study selection

Pilot testing

We performed pilot testing prior to study selection. Inclusion and exclusion criteria were created and used for the 'two-step' approach of study selection – 'title and abstract' screening and 'full-text' review. In pilot tests, each article required agreement from at least three independent reviewers to be included. When a disagreement occurred, it was resolved by a fourth reviewer and follow-up discussion. This step helps reviewers to reduce uncertainties or ambiguity as well as to refine the inclusion-exclusion criteria if needed.

For instance, prior the beginning of the actual screening, pilot tests were conducted among four raters (WN, CJ, AN, and SS) were achieved on the same 175 random articles in total to ensure that titles and abstracts were retrieved in accordance with the inclusion/exclusion criteria. All disagreements were solved by the options as mentioned.

Furthermore, the agreement among reviewers in the process of article screening and selection has been measured using the interrater reliability (IRR). Interrater agreement is managed as follows: if the IRR value is greater than or equal to 0.80, which indicates a high or strong level of agreement;⁷³ ⁷⁴ articles with a high score were advanced to the next stage of the study framework. In cases where the IRR value is less than 0.80, which indicates low or poor level of agreement),⁷³ ⁷⁴ then the reconciliation of refining inclusion-exclusion criteria and pilot tests would come into play; the refining criteria and testing would be repeatedly taken until the level of agreement reaches the IRR threshold of 0.80. We have applied our interrater agreement protocol into the pilot testing,

the study selection (title-abstract screening and full-text review) stage, including an upcoming stage of data extraction.

Screening and selection

In total, 2877 search records were imported to Covidence (Melbourne, Victoria, Australia; <https://www.covidence.org/>), a web-based collaboration software platform for study selection. The selection is a required component of the *two-step* process, beginning by examining titles and abstracts (*primary* screening) and subsequently full-text articles (*secondary* screening). After the full-text review is completed, a final set of the selected articles will be eligible for data extraction. The reasons for excluding an article during the selection process will be indicated and reported. Note that during the actual screening and selection processes, each article requires agreement from at least two independent reviewers in order to be selected. Discrepancies were resolved by the decision of a third reviewer and subsequent analysis of the reasons of disagreement among all reviewers.

Overall, records at each stage of the study selection starting from searching, title-abstract screening and full-text review, until final selection for data extraction will be summarized and presented in a PRISMA flowchart.⁷⁵ This review has been ongoing. At the time when the protocol was prepared, the review was in the title and abstract screening process.

Stage IV. Data extraction

Data extraction will be conducted in selected articles after full-text review by utilizing the 'PICO' – Population, Intervention, Comparison groups, Outcomes model.^{76 77} A data charting form will be developed under an iterative process in order to capture variables relevant to our review questions, and is expected to be refined, if needed, during the data extraction process. Extracted data will be collected using the data collection tools such as Covidence (<https://www.covidence.org/>) and Google Forms (Google LLC, Mountain View, CA, USA) and recorded in a tubular format with textual description using the spreadsheet software such as Microsoft Excel (Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA, USA) and Google Sheets (Google LLC).

Each paper requires at least two reviewers independently charting data items to ensure the accuracy and consistency of all required/relevant information. Pilot tests of data extraction will be employed among all reviewers on at least the same 30 randomly eligible full-text articles. Extracted data will be compared. The agreement of data extraction will be assessed throughout the data extraction process with an interrater agreement (IRR) threshold of greater than or equal to 0.80. Any controversies or disagreements will be solved by a third reviewer and discussion.

We will extract and record data in table form. Extracted data will define details as follows: (i) **basic study** information (authors, year of publication, locations/countries where studies were conducted), and (ii) **specific study** information (study populations, aims, designs and experimental details, and outcomes/key findings related or relevant to our review questions). Among all eligible articles, we prioritize a sub-group of those that specifically used iPSCs derived from humans; those will be extracted exclusive data as acquainting information of the implication of human iPSC model. The table outline and contents will be developed and justified based on the information obtained throughout the data extraction process. These materials will be used in next step of the data analysis. A draft of data charting form is displayed in **Table 1**.

Stage V. Data analysis and presentation

The plan for data analysis and presentation will be developed and adjusted upon the data contents until the data collection is final. Following data charting, we will mainly use qualitative analysis to describe and use the summary of the data (see data items in **Table 1**) extracted from all included articles to report the analyzing results by narrative and descriptive approaches aligning with our scoping review objectives and questions. Quantitative data analysis will be used to mainly summarize the results in the form of number and percentage. Transcribed texts, tables, charts, and figures will be presented when appropriate. Sub-group presentation will be considered and summarized according to the review questions. To keep the standard of scoping review, we will follow the PRISMA-ScR^{65 66} guideline to report our results.

Our data presentation aims to provide the summarizing evidence-based information in response to the specific review questions, and then to allow reviewers to identify the knowledge gaps as well as formulate the attribution of iPSC approaches to future substance use or addiction research. We will not perform the assessment of either the methodological quality or the risk of bias across articles. Not to mention both assessments are not required according to a scoping review methodological guideline.^{62 64 65}

Stage VI. Collaborative consultation

We plan to collaborate and seek feedback on the data of our scoping review from academic and research experts in stem cell research in addition to substance use or addiction area. We expect their comparative aspect to refine the analysis report. We would like to get their comments on the feature of the iPSC model, including gaps and roadblocks along with recommendations and prospects for its applications based on our collective evidence. This information will be useful in highlighting and directing the role of iPSC approach and how to enhance the utilization of iPSC model, particularly the human iPSCs, in future research of substance use and disorders.

ETHICS & DISSEMINATION

This scoping review does not involve human or living subjects, therefore, there are no need for ethical approval or informed consent. The result of our scoping review will be summarized and reported in a peer-review publication as well as an academic or scientific conference presentation.

LIMITATIONS

The findings of the current study should be interpreted in light of several limitation. First, our review is limited by the inclusion and exclusion criteria. ESCs are excluded from our search strategy as our focus on host-derived iPSCs, so our findings only correspond to iPSC method, not the entire stem cell technologies. Second, although our review aims at wide-ranging health outcomes that relevant to addictive substances, our findings are not reflective of patient- or treatment-oriented studies that use iPSCs to mainly examine the efficacy or response of various therapeutic agents/drugs. Third, our review is also limited to studies published in English – as such, only a

fraction of the topic-related literature is summarized. Next, we will not evaluate the quality of methodologies or evidence across included papers as these are not required in a scoping review.⁶²
^{64 65} Consequently, we do not intend to point out any indicators of study quality or the quality of technique protocols. Lastly, our findings will not serve as a proposed guidance or practical protocol, but rather report the broad description and potential gaps of the approach of iPSC into substance addiction fields.

CONCLUSIONS

A scoping review is an intuitive, systematic approach to identifying the available literature relevant to the topic of interest. We conduct a scoping review to map and present existing evidence in the nature of iPSC approach in substance use/addiction research, from the primary research articles published in the last 15 years. Based on the review questions, we expect our review results to provide the role and involvement of iPSC model in substance use research area.

To our knowledge, this is the first review that will show comprehensive evidence specifically covering a broad range of basic knowledge, interplay, and gap in using iPSCs to a wide variety of addictive substances. Therefore, this information will advance our knowledge and help to outline future directions and challenges using iPSCs. Moreover, as our topic is more engaged in scientific research than patient- or clinical-oriented research, we hope that scoping reviews will be augmented into basic scientific research for evidence synthesis whenever there are proper indications.^{55 57 58}

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Author contributions:

Guarantor: corresponding authors, WN and RHCP. Conceptualization: WN and RHCP. Methodology: WN, SRP, and RHCP. Software: WN and RHCP. Validation: WN, CJ, AN, and SS. Formal Analysis: WN, CJ, AN, and SS. Investigation: WN, SRP, CJ, AN, and SS. Resources: RHCP. Data Curation: WN, SRP, CJ, AN, SS, and RHCP. Visualization: WN. Writing – Original Draft Preparation: WN and SRP. Writing – Review and Editing: WN, SRP, CJ, AN, SS, and RHCP. Supervision: RHCP. Project Administration: WN. Funding Acquisition: RHCP.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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TABLE

Table 1. A draft of data extraction form.

General Information		
	Variables	Description
Article information	Authors' names	Name of authors
	Authors' affiliations and locations	Institutes/countries where authors were affiliated with
	Year of publication	Year of the article published
	Article title	Title of the article
	Journal name	Journal that the article published
	Scope(s) of journal	Scopes of a journal that the article was published
	Article type	Type of the article published: primary research, systematic review, meta-analysis
	Language	Language of the article published
Study information	Study site(s)	The place(s) (countries) where the study was conducted and/or where the sample recruitment took place
	Study designs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Observational study Experimental study
	Study setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Basic research Clinical research
	Study aim(s)	Aim of the study
	Study method(s)	Methods used in the study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>iPSC model</i>: alone/combined with other models <i>Additional models</i> (if applicable)
	Study samples: primary and secondary (if applicable)	Samples of the study: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <i>Primary samples</i>: iPSC hosts <i>Secondary samples (including species, number, condition, age, and sex, if applicable)</i>: samples used in other models, in addition to iPSC method
	Main study finding(s)	Each main finding of the study, of which <u>not all</u> may or <i>may not</i> be relevant to our review questions
	Main finding measurement(s)	Each main finding assessment and unit (if applicable)
	Study conclusions	Conclusions of the study, which <i>may</i> or <i>may not</i> be relevant to our review questions
	Study challenges/caveats	Challenges/caveats of the study, which <i>may</i> or <i>may not</i> be relevant to our review questions
Specific Information		
	Variables	Description
Primary sample information (Participants) Details are specific to primary samples, defined as iPSC hosts	Sample type	Species of iPSC hosts: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Humans Primates Non-primate mammals: mice, pigs Non-mammals: <i>C. elegans</i>, zebra fish
	Sample size	Number of iPSC hosts
	Sample health condition	iPSC hosts' health conditions: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Healthy Specific underlying diseases or health/medical conditions (if applicable): for example, chronic lung diseases, cirrhosis, and cancers, etc.
	Age (if applicable)	iPSC hosts' age (mean, if applicable): days/months/years

	Sex (if applicable)	iPSC hosts' sex: male/female
	Ethnicity (if applicable)	iPSC hosts' ethnicity: African/Asian/European, etc.
<p>iPSC model information (Concept - #1)</p> <p>Details are specific to iPSC model used in the study</p>	Structure of iPSCs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2D • 3D (organoid)
	Original tissue type	Type of tissues obtained from iPSC hosts: for example, lymphoblasts, fibroblasts, and epithelial cells, etc.
	Terminal differentiation tissue type	Type of derived tissues after reprogramming stage: for example, alveolar cells, hepatocytes, and neurons, etc.
	Reprogramming technique	<p>Type of reprogramming transfer system^a</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrative transfer system: viral, non-viral • Non-integrative transfer system: viral, non-viral
<p>Substance information (Concept - #2)</p> <p>Details are specific to additive substances that used in the study</p>	Type of substances	<p>Type of substance [defined following the resources^{b-d}]:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alcohol/ethanol • Amphetamine/methamphetamine • Cannabis/marijuana/cannabinoids • Cigarette/nicotine/tobacco • Cocaine • Opioids/heroin • Synthetic opioids: methadone, naloxone • Psychostimulant drugs: methylphenidate (Adderall®, Ritalin®) • Hallucinogens: LSD, PCP • Depressants: benzodiazepines • Tranquilizers: ketamine • Other illicit drugs: ecstasy (MDMA), MDA, MPTP, kratom, etc.
	Categories of substances	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alcohol, cigarette, e-cigarette • Controlled substances (defined as an illegal or prescription drug regulated by the Controlled Substances Act (CSA) in the U.S.) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◦ Narcotic/Non-narcotic ◦ Prescribed/Non-prescribed
	Exposure setting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>In vitro</i> • <i>In vivo</i>
	Duration of exposure (depend on the exposure setting)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short-term/long-term (if applicable) • Days/months/years (if applicable)
	Route of exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Direct exposure: <i>in vitro</i> exposure, drinking, ingestion, injection, smoking • Indirect exposure: prenatal exposure
	<p>Outcome information (Concept - #3)</p> <p>Details are specific to the study outcomes relevant to the review questions (i.e., substances-related health outcomes)</p>	Relevant outcomes
Relevant outcome measurement		Assessment of results/findings relevant to the review questions
<p>Specific challenges/caveats</p> <p>Details are specific to the review questions</p>	Relevant challenges/caveats	This challenges/caveats specific or related to any of our review questions or 'PCC' ^{e,f} elements

iPSCs, induced pluripotent stem cells

PCC, refers to 'Participants', 'Concept', and 'Context', respectively, defined by the Joanne Briggs Institute (JBI) guideline for conducting scoping reviews^{e,f}

^a Al Abbar A, Ngai SC, Nograles N, et al. Induced pluripotent stem cells: reprogramming platforms and applications in cell replacement therapy. *Biores Open Access* 2020;9(1):121-36.

^b National Institute on Drug Abuse. Commonly used drugs charts [Internet]. Research topics. Rockville, MD: NIDA, National Institutes of Health; c2022 [updated 2020 Aug 20; cited 2022 Mar 4]. [about 4 screens]. Available from: <https://nida.nih.gov/research-topics/commonly-used-drugs-charts>

^c Substance Abuse and Mental Health Services Administration. Key substance use and mental health indicators in the United States: results from the 2021 National Survey on Drug Use and Health (HHS Publication No. PEP22-07-01-005, NSDUH Series H-57) [Internet]. Rockville, MD: Center for Behavioral Health Statistics and Quality, SAMHSA; 2022 [updated Dec 2022; cited 2023 Feb 5]. [about 100 screens]. Available from: <https://www.samhsa.gov/data/report/2021-nsduh-annual-national-report>

^d United States Drug Enforcement Administration. Controlled substances - alphabetical order [Online document]. Drug information, The Controlled Substances Act. Springfield, VA: United States DEA, U.S. Department of Justice; c2023 [updated 2023 Jan 5; cited 2023 Jan 29]. [19 pages]. Available from: https://www.deadiversion.usdoj.gov/schedules/orangebook/c_cs_alpha.pdf

^ePeters MD, Godfrey CM, McInerney P, et al. *The Joanna Briggs Institute reviewers' manual 2015: methodology for JBI scoping reviews*. Adelaide, SA, Australia: JBI 2015. 24 p.

^fPeters MDJ, Godfrey C, McInerney P, et al. Chapter 11: Scoping reviews [Internet]. In: Aromataris E, Munn Z, eds. *JBI manual for evidence synthesis (2020 version)*. Adelaide, Australia: JBI; 2020 [updated 2022 Jul 26; cited 2022 Mar 4]. [Online document]. Available from: <https://synthesismanual.jbi.global> doi:10.46658/JBIMES-20-12